

ANALYZING ECONOMIC DYNAMICS IN RESOURCE ALLOCATION FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: *In the ever-evolving landscape of urban development, the role of resources remains pivotal. This research delves into the dynamic relationship between emerging resources and the tertiary industry, offering a fresh perspective from the vantage point of urban planning. As society's demands for resources continue to expand and diversify, it becomes imperative to reevaluate the supply and allocation of these resources to sustain urban growth. Unlike traditional sectors, the tertiary industry presents a unique set of challenges and opportunities, intertwined with urban development. This study explores the intricate connections between industrial energy efficiency, value, output, and urban scale, transcending the traditional boundaries of economic analysis. By addressing the resource needs of the tertiary industry and aligning them with urban planning strategies, we aim to shed light on new pathways to overcome the urban development bottlenecks. This interdisciplinary approach offers a comprehensive view of how urban areas can harness emerging resources to foster sustainable growth.*

Keywords: *urban planning, resource allocation, tertiary industry, emerging resources, urban development, sustainability.*

1. Introduction

Since ancient times, people have needed to rely on primary natural resources because of the resources of everyday needs. Therefore, resources are the fundamental guarantees of the Development of human society. Urban planning also needs to sift through the reallocation of resources. However, with the continuous improvement of science and technology and national policies, the distribution of natural resources is now expanded. At the same time, unlike the resources required by agriculture and industry that society in the past, emerging resources and industrial types are constantly filled with society, and national and social Development has new needs. Therefore, at the moment, examining the demand, supply and supply of new resources and the tertiary industry, and the configuration problem is an important entry point for solving the bottleneck of Urban Development. However, most of the current research on the tertiary industry is primarily economic experts, and only some think about it from the perspective of urban planning. The conclusions obtained in this article are mostly the relationship between industrial energy efficiency, value, output value and urban size, and less strategic analysis,

2. Natural resources and industries

2.1 Human resources in natural resources

In philosophy or physics, natural resources refer to the substance, an objective existence that does not use human will as a transfer. From an economic perspective, natural resources include human resources and non-human resources [4-6]. Human resources refer to resources that humans have used and are using. For example, land that is planted, mine that is mined and the accumulation of human

wealth and the labor skills of human beings. The so-called non-human resources refer to the resources humans cannot reach, such as outer space and deep-seated earth resources.

Furthermore, human beings have yet to recognize resources that can be reached, even the Development of human intellectual potential. The capital article is studied based on the correlation between urban Development and resources, so only considering human resources closely related to the city. Profit resources are the sum of human survival's production and living materials, including mineral resources, environmental resources, land, tools, crops, food, energy, capital, etc. Human resources are human.

Labor, including physical labor and mental work. In the process of urban Development, human resources are an essential impact factor. In the urban network supported by modern technology today, material resources can be easily distributed to various cities. Therefore, the attractiveness of physical resources is reduced to increase the demand for human resources. Physical resources process human resources. With the abundant material resources, human resources pros and cons will play the city's future Development. Crucial role[7-9].

2.2 Three industrial compositions in modern cities

The three industries are a Western economic theory. Western economists divide the national economic department into three industries according to the order of labor objectives: agriculture, industry, and other industries, except for the first and second industries. Until 2013, the National Bureau of Statistics of China clarified the three industries. According to the Classification of the National Economic Industry (GB/T 4754—2011):

The first industry refers to agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry, and fisheries (excluding agriculture, forestry, animal husbandry, and fishing service industry).

The second industry refers to the mining industry (excluding mining auxiliary activities), manufacturing (excluding metal products, machinery and equipment repair industry), power, thermal, gas, water and water production and supply industry, and construction industry.

The tertiary industry is the service industry, which refers to the abolition of industries other than the first and second industries. The tertiary industry includes the wholesale and retail industry, transportation, warehousing and postal industry, accommodation and catering, information transmission, software and information technology services, financial industry, real estate, leasing and business services, scientific research and technical services, Animal Husbandry and Fisheries' business, mining assistance activities in the mining industry, and metal products, machinery and equipment repair industry in manufacturing.

With the changes in the times, the possibility of urban development increases, and the scope of resource distribution of railway and water transportation can be more convenient to integrate resource integration in a more extensive range. For example, the first and second industries must rely on the first and second industries to ensure urban Development.

2.3 The correlation between industrial and urban Development

Cases of industrial settlement are common. Since ancient times, the wealthy areas of the agricultural industry have always been populated. Rivers, green spaces, and fertile soil must be considered when settlement. In the era of industrialization, according to the multi-country development model proposed by experts, the relationship between industrialization and urbanization has experienced the evolution process from tight to relaxation. Industrialization is the initial driving force of urbanization. Urbanization promoted by industrialization will develop faster than industrialization, showing the stage of industrialization and urban scale [10]. Industrial agglomeration is the initial motivation for industrialization and the result of industrial Development. Industry gathers in the connotation and surpassing industrial categories, including the concentration of production factors such as labor and

capital in a broader sense. Through population agglomeration driven by industrial agglomeration and economic activities, the urbanization process has been deepened, and the scale of urban scale has increased. The size of a particular city is a guarantee of the consumer market, so it forms a promotion cycle. However, the increase in scale will also bring congestion, so industrial operations and personnel living costs have increased, and industrial profits have also declined, which has caused some industries to start flowing out—some industries to check in, which will evolve in the industry. The industry's evolution also affects urban leading directions, development goals, and vision planning changes. Therefore, urban Development is closely related to the industrial distribution of the city and the surrounding area (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The association structure of the industry and urban Development

3. Research Research Research on the Development of Contemporary City, Transformation and Resource Impact

3.1 The relationship between traffic resources and small and medium-sized urban Development

(This figure is referenced from

http://userimages11.51sole.com/20160722/b_3168668_201607221133549505.jpg)

Figure 2: China Eight Vertical Eight Heng Railway Planning Map

French economists have proposed the "growth pole theory" and "growth center theory," and some German scholars led by Sombart have proposed the "growth axis theory." Some domestic scholars in the late 1990s based on the foreign traffic economic axis theory, and combined the "growth pole theory" and "growth axis theory" combined with China's actual situation, proposed the "traffic economic belt theory." Facilities construction can not only form new economic growth points but also optimize the configuration and flow of the elements, radiate the economy in the surrounding areas, and promote coordinated Development in various regions. The emergence of high-speed rail has dramatically

shortened the time and distance between cities in China [11], which has a significant role in promoting developed cities. China's eight vertical eight -horizontal railway planning profoundly impacts the road city. However, according to the study of well-known scholars, although the emergence of high-speed rail significantly promotes the Development of large and developed cities, the gap between small and medium-sized cities has widened. Promote the circulation of talents. First-tier cities such as Beijing, Shanghai, Guangzhou, and Shenzhen also use policies to assist in the rotation and elimination of Talent. Many people who leave can be effectively absorbed into other cities and form a second integration of human resources. Among them, the guiding role of high-speed rail lines is undeniable. In today's society, the importance of human resources is increasingly prominent, and such a guiding role is positive. Therefore, the influence of transportation resources is irreplaceable, and the high-speed rail transportation line breaks the completely controlled situation of the original big city, making the exchanges between resources more broadly, as shown in Figure 2.

3.2 Resource utilization and resource dry city transformation

The "National Sustainable Development Plan for resource-based cities" (2013 ~ 2020) issued by the State Council specifies the names of Chinese resource-based cities in detail. According to scholars' research on 24 resource-based cities, the per capita GDP of resource-based cities from 2000 to 2012 is calculated, and the formula used is the evolution of the Tel Index and the Geni coefficient formula. Main reason. With the year-on-year changes [14], the shortage of different resources has threatened long-term economic construction. The single industrial structure has also become essential in restricting resource-based cities and destroying the ecological resource environment. Therefore, the transformation of resource-exhausted cities has also gradually stabilized the current secondary industry and the era of booming tertiary industries. In the cases of foreign transformations, ecological reconstruction and repair should be attached to the environmental protection and long-term mechanisms. The combination of industrial development funds and ecological environment restoration funds, disaster governance funds, personnel training funds, and industrial heritage tourism development funds are combined. For example, Ruhr, Germany, pays attention to environmental restoration and industrial heritage tourism.

On the one hand, the intervention of ecological policy restores urban greening to strengthen urban infrastructure. In the second aspect, through the intervention of new industries, part of the labor force is transferred to ensure the balance of jobs, revenue, and expenditure in urban Development—an environmental style caused by the industrial city's trauma. At the same time, the industrial heritage has been retained, becoming a regional landmark and cultural relic, and then injecting a new vitality mechanism into a medium, developing new industrial models such as tourism, cultural and creative, and so on, thereby forming a reasonable recovery mechanism.

3.3 World Fair and Coastal City Development

Research on the population density of the coastal areas based on the data of "China Statistical Yearbook 2010" (Figure 3, Figure 4). The natural environment, economic conditions, and policy support are the main influencing factors among them. In the current world pattern, in the era of the rise of the Chinese market, these three mainly rely on policy influence and opening up foreign trade to form a role of driving human resources, thereby creating economic conditions and gradually forming a virtuous cycle -economic attraction of talents, Talent drives the economy. However, after this period of time, the introduction of a large number of people has also caused dilemmas in the Development of coastal cities: the shortage of housing, pressure on employment competition, and environmental pollution. This kind of coastal city is currently inclined to guide the orderly flow of population, increase the power of the environment and population, and form a sustainable development of resources and the environment.

(This figure is referenced by Fu Yuexin, Chen Yingying, and Zhang Zhenke. *The spatiotemporal changes of population density in coastal cities in China from 1985 to 2010. Tropical Geography, 2014, 34 (5): 635-642*)

Figure 3: 1985-2010 The total population of the coastal cities and the proportion of the population in the country

(This figure is referenced by Fu Yuexin, Chen Yingying, and Zhang Zhenke. *The spatiotemporal changes of population density in coastal cities in China from 1985 to 2010. Tropical Geography, 2014, 34 (5): 635-642*)

Figure 4: The average population density of the coastal cities in the coastal cities in 1985-2010

The Development of non-traditional resource cities is moving towards a new peak. The attractiveness of resource-based cities is gradually fading. Instead, it is a "resource platform city," a resource trade operation city.

4. Urban Development and prospects under the new resource distribution method

4.1 National logistics platform distribution and influence

According to research, Shanghai, Beijing, Shenyang, Zhengzhou, Chongqing, Kunming, and Guangzhou are the first-level logistics node cities of high-speed rail logistics bases. Hangzhou, Chengdu, Wuhan, Qingdao, Tianjin, Fuzhou, Harbin, Urumqi, Lanzhou, Nanjing and other provincial capitals and economies. The center is a secondary logistics node; the other 118 million people have high-speed rail logistics sites [12-13]. China Express Products mainly produce three-step layout forms. From east to west, there is the three-level staircase, which is mainly concentrated in coastal areas. At the same time, the central region is divergent by the provincial capital, and the western region takes Chengdu and Chongqing as the main distribution center. Under the traction of railway transportation, trading resources can effectively play a role in the eastern half of China and also make trade-based coastal cities develop rapidly. The continuous improvement of the intercity railway has strengthened the resource transportation network of railway transportation. Therefore, in the current planning period of each city,

the problem of the insertion of railway transportation network nodes will be considered during the current planning period.

4.2 Urban activity under the action of information network and logistics platform

The emergence of the railway network realizes the transfer of more resources to multiple points and facilitates the trade between resource points. The Development of the information network has made regional resources no longer restricted by cities, liberating the regional restrictions of human resources, and people can achieve different land operations through the interactive office of network information. As a result, the city has changed from the attraction of human resources from the economic benefits of the early second industries to the attraction of urban value to human resources. Urban Development has begun to diversify and needs more attention to the industrial economy. The gathering of environment, culture, services, and even human resources has become an essential factor that attracts human resources. Because of the dual role of the Internet's information network and logistics platform, the Development of Urban Development is flexible and diverse, ensuring that cities can continue to maintain Development. At the same time, the development space and future development direction of different types of cities have been given. Ecological cities, cultural cities, tourist cities, tourism cities, and even comprehensive giant cities can be realized on this basis, indicating the future city's Development and possibility.

5. Conclusion and revelation

From the economics perspective, this article clarifies that in the case of abundant material resources, the pros and cons of human resources play a vital role in the city's future Development. In the current developed environment, the resource allocation method is more flexible, No longer subject to geographical restrictions. At the same time, with the booming Development of the tertiary industry, the attention of human resources, the standard role of the logistics platform and the information network, urban Development has emerged as a new situation in diversification and comprehensiveness. In the historical process, inspiration can be obtained.

1) The current material resource allocation is flexible, so human resources become a critical factor in urban Development. How to ensure the reasonable introduction and resettlement of human resources will be the primary goal. Creating urban ecology, culture, and various industrial platforms, gives a broader space for human resources. It is people-oriented, mainly based on the effectiveness of industrial effects, and gradually shifts to human energy efficiency.

2) To be more convenient for the circulation and allocation of material resources, setting traffic nodes and logistics platforms is an essential goal of solving future urban Development. The information network has achieved a national link and is in line with the world. Regarding material circulation channels, urban planning and perspective should be planned and designed from the perspective of the country and even the world. The potential value of use can achieve a large-scale global planning collaboration.

3) In the case of flexible human resources circulation, minor and medium-sized cities can attract corresponding human resources through the support policies of the tertiary industry. To realize the new situation in which a large city is a comprehensive center and a new situation of mutual benefit around the lack of items in large cities.

At the same time, there are also hidden, complicated factors in such an environment.

1) The weakening of the regional restrictions on material resources makes human resources eastward. Individual cities have become the direction of the middle of the year in the middle of the year, and there is a trend of contemporary immigration. However, unlike ancient policy immigrants, the

spontaneous immigration wave lacks a global vision. It is easy to cause national imbalanced Development but affects resource allocation, which requires appropriate intervention.

2) The significant comparison of coastal and western cities is the distribution of trade networks. It is also the border between national borders. How to open a trading platform through the Western route, such as the Silk Road, will also be the top priority of future urban Development.

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